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Positivity and higher alertness levels facilitate discovery: Longitudinal sentiment analysis of emotions on Twitter[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Emotions stimulate and shape entrepreneurial alertness. In a first U.S.-based study, we analyzed self-reports of entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs by measuring differences in valence in emotions using the frequently applied Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS) scale for trait affectivity. In a second study, we explored 28,478 tweets of 185 successful entrepreneurs and 264 non-entrepreneurs (both drawn from *Forbes* lists) from 2009 to 2021, categorizing their tweeted words into positive and negative based on the Harvard IV-4 dictionary. While the model of Study 1 stresses that examples of positiveness, such as interested, excited, enthusiastic, and inspired, facilitate entrepreneurial alertness levels, which in turn accelerate levels of entrepreneurial discovery, Study 2's sentiment analysis highlights the significant difference between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs' word usage—successful entrepreneurs tend to use more positive words in their tweets than successful non-entrepreneurs. Our results aim to inform and inspire entrepreneurial educators, policymakers, and (potential) entrepreneurs regarding how positiveness shapes entrepreneurial alertness, which promotes the discovery of potential new business ideas.

1. Introduction

“Be on the alert to recognize your prime at whatever time of your life it may occur.” Muriel Spark

The research field of entrepreneurship has continually created (e) motions—that is, generated studies regarding the role of positive and negative affect—across diverse entrepreneurial topics (e.g., [Cardon et al., 2012](#); [Warnick et al., 2018](#)). While positive affect refers to positive emotions and expressions, negative affect refers to negative emotions ([Watson et al., 1988](#)). Emotions represent the heart of entrepreneurship because they enable entrepreneurs to foster and tap into creativity and lead to exploration and exploitation of business opportunities ([Baron, 2007](#); [Cardon et al., 2013](#)). Previous entrepreneurship research has shown that different emotions can have varied impacts on entrepreneurial decisions (e.g., [Chen et al., 2009](#)). In this context, emotions can fuel individuals' levels of alertness to get started entrepreneurially; that

is, they act as antecedents ([Tang et al., 2012](#)). The *Oxford Learner's Dictionary*¹ defines alertness “as the fact of being aware of something, especially a problem or danger.” From the entrepreneurial perspective, such a “problem” or “danger” might be viewed as an opportunity by the entrepreneur's emotions. More precisely, individuals with higher entrepreneurial alertness have been described as more aware and possessing a kind of “antenna” that is stimulated by their emotions and permits specific recognition of gaps ([Kirzner, 1979](#)). Those individuals are uniquely prepared to consistently scan the environment and create or discover opportunities ([Kaish and Gilad, 1991](#)). [Kirzner \(1979\)](#) characterizes alertness as the skill of identifying opportunities unnoticed by others. Thus, we expect emotions to have an influence on discovering entrepreneurial opportunities via alertness.

Who cares? Because entrepreneurship is essential for generating job-rich, inclusive economic growth ([Galindo and Méndez, 2014](#)), knowing how new entrepreneurial opportunities are discovered is useful for both scholarly and practical purposes ([Shane, 2000](#); [Short et al.,](#)

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¹ <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/us/definition/english/alertness>.

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2010). Knowledge of which emotions facilitate entrepreneurial alertness (Tang et al., 2012), and particularly those that encourage nascent entrepreneurs to start a venture, attract sources of finance, and pursue an entrepreneurial career, would constitute a significant advance in our research field, because scientists could then develop, test, and implement tools that could help emotionally train potential entrepreneurs to be more alert to entrepreneurial actions. Furthermore, as entrepreneurs tend to communicate more positively in public (Waters et al., 2021), such emotions could also serve as an indicator of the entrepreneur's emotional state of mind to successfully cope with risks. Even more importantly and at a general level, a more detailed understanding of whether positive or negative emotions—that is, how entrepreneurs feel on average—are better for entrepreneurial discovery is nothing less than crucial.

In entrepreneurship, our understanding of the phenomenon of discovery is critical and might include how different individuals discover new business opportunities. With crowdsourcing platforms on the rise, entrepreneurship scholars have adopted an inclusive lens to raise several questions regarding the formative discovery processes of the entrepreneurship research domain (Mitchell et al., 2004). These fundamental questions have traditional roots. For instance, Kirzner (1973, 1999) directly addressed discovery in a dynamic and inclusive economy, while Schumpeter indirectly tackled discovery by making scientists inventors and entrepreneurs rather than mere innovators (McMullen and Shepherd, 2006). This influence and support by others, whether entrepreneurs or non-entrepreneurs, on crowdfunding platforms highlights the importance of identifying mechanisms on how emotions shape alertness and discovery.

What do we and don't we know? Lanivich et al.'s (2022) recent investigation of the concept of entrepreneurial alertness reveals inconsistencies and emerging trends in the field. Entrepreneurial alertness contributes to cognition-based theories regarding opportunities by representing a specific cognitive ability of entrepreneurs in contrast to non-entrepreneurs: the skill of sensing ideas relevant for entrepreneurial activities and ventures. Entrepreneurial alertness has also been described as “the application of unique schemata that allow the entrepreneur to impute meaning to environmental change”; consequently, alertness arises from schematic differences in changing conditions (Valliere, 2013, p. 430). Lanivich et al. (2022) provide a precise conceptualization of entrepreneurial alertness that enables the exploration of emotion and cognition in the context of entrepreneurial opportunities conducted by already successful entrepreneurs. Building on previous efforts (Shepherd et al., 2019), the present study is the first major effort to address the antecedents to alertness with the final outcome of discovery.

In principle, entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs—that is, anyone in our society—can stimulate and shape the discovery of entrepreneurial opportunities (Hitt et al., 2012). For the sake of clarity, an entrepreneur in the present study is defined as someone who founded and is running a small business and still owns 100% of the shares (adapted from Koudstaal et al., 2016). Whereas entrepreneurs are those actively pursuing an entrepreneurial endeavor, non-entrepreneurs are those who might inspire entrepreneurs but are not themselves active entrepreneurs (e.g., influencers, data scientists, technical program managers). Furthermore, non-entrepreneurs could turn into entrepreneurs depending on their emotions, alertness, and future opportunities for discovery. Researchers stress that the synergistic interactions between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs boost entrepreneurial initiatives (Rasmussen and Borch, 2010). Likewise, scientists (Landry et al., 2010) and policymakers (European Commission, 2013) have called for further research into entrepreneurial alertness and discovery.

The core motivation for this study has two central roots, each of which is formulated as a question. (1) *How does alertness facilitate entrepreneurial discovery?* Contemporary studies lack explanations of the antecedents of entrepreneurial discovery and specifically do not sufficiently consider entrepreneurial alertness. The more we know about

different levels of alertness and discovery between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs, the better we will be able to explore how to train the alertness levels of non-entrepreneurs toward the levels found among entrepreneurs, which is expected to facilitate entrepreneurial discovery. (2) *Is positive or negative affect a better source to stimulate one's level of alertness?* Overall, our knowledge regarding the role of emotions in alertness and the influence of alertness levels on discovering entrepreneurial opportunities remains limited (Tang et al., 2012). Because prior work argues that emotions can facilitate entrepreneurial alertness (Tang et al., 2012), we might assume that different levels of positive and negative emotional traits among entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs could facilitate alertness and thus an individual's potential for entrepreneurial discovery. We expect (at least some) entrepreneurs to be primarily positive people, a trait that has the potential to facilitate their level of alertness, which Tang et al. (2012) report to be teachable. However, because prior research also shows that dissatisfaction leads to discovery (Herron and Sapienza, 1992; Zhou, 2008), it is not clear that a positive trait has beneficial effects over a longer time period. Furthermore, Tang et al. (2012) argue that “outcome variables also need to examine the entrepreneurial alertness process and their impact” and ask questions like “it seems highly plausible that higher levels of entrepreneurial alertness are also likely to lead to the identification of more new ideas; but is that actually the case?” (p. 92). That said, although some time has passed since these remarks were published, there are still mixed results in research as to whether higher levels of alertness correlate to more elevated levels of entrepreneurial discovery. We might expect entrepreneurs to show higher levels of alertness and discovery, backed by success as evidence, but other empirical evidence of such a connection with emotions remains scant. Moreover, we might assume a causal effect of emotions as a point of departure, but entrepreneurial studies have not explored whether entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs show significant differences in emotional states, which might be a baseline for alertness to discovery.

What will we learn? To overcome the gaps in existing research, the present study aims to make the following consensus-building contributions (Grant and Pollock, 2011). (1) We seek to answer whether entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs show different levels of different emotions as a basis for different alertness levels. Moreover, we examine whether those levels interact differently with entrepreneurial alertness and entrepreneurial discovery among entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs. (2) Because alertness has been identified as an ability that can be taught and improved over time (Tang et al., 2012), the practical implications of our work on alertness can support nascent entrepreneurs in learning how to discover potential business opportunities by becoming aware of how their emotions affect their entrepreneurial alertness levels. By investigating whether positive and negative emotions stimulate the alertness levels of entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs, we can assess the contributions of different emotions to alertness and how they do—or do not—facilitate entrepreneurial discovery. In particular, we suggest that non-alert would-be entrepreneurs could be trained to be more positive and thus raise their alertness levels. (3) Finally, previous investigations exploring the impact of entrepreneurial alertness on discovery have been weakened by their limited empirical aspects. For example, Ardichvili et al. (2003) provided a first draft of a theory of entrepreneurial alertness but did not carry out empirical investigations to support or refine that theory. Valliere (2013) also outlined a theory of entrepreneurial alertness but did not include any empirical evidence. We thus aim to move the research field forward and verify these theoretical foundations by replicating research on entrepreneurial alertness by testing Kirzner's (1979) alertness theory and McMullen and Shepherd's (2006) later development of alertness across entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs and taking their different emotions into consideration, as proposed by Tang et al. (2012). In this context, Kirzner's (1973, 1999) cognition theory lies at the theoretical heart of our research project. By comparing entrepreneurs to non-entrepreneurs in two complementary studies, we explain a general

mechanism of entrepreneurial discovery. In this framework, we argue that entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs are by nature differently alert to entrepreneurial discovery, which can be affected by positive and negative emotions. The following research question shapes this study: *How do entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs differ in their levels of alertness and discovery, taking emotions into account?*

To answer our research question, we conduct two complementary studies. First, in a survey we use self-reported indicators of emotion as instruments for entrepreneurial alertness and then estimate the impact of this estimated alertness on discovery. We also investigate the differences between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs in our variables under investigation—positive and negative affect, entrepreneurial alertness, and entrepreneurial discovery—and explain the linear relationship between alertness and the discovery of new ideas, in line with previous efforts (e.g., Tang et al., 2012). To measure positive and negative traits, we applied the original PANAS scale by Watson et al. (1988) using mood-related adjectives. We measure differences in valence in emotions by using the frequently applied PANAS scale for trait affectivity. Although some examples, such as “excited,” “jittery,” or “upset,” connote short-term conditions, we asked questions so as to highlight the general emotional tendency of our subjects. Thus, in this first study we use the PANAS scale as a trait. Second, we conducted a field study and used text sentiment analysis to explore 28,478 Twitter posts by 185 successful entrepreneurs and 264 non-entrepreneurs over at least 10 years. Studies testing differences in emotions between successful entrepreneurs and others have not yet used text sentiments comparing real-world social media posts between the two groups under investigation in a longitudinal context, so using those measures can help provide a more nuanced explanation.

This work is organized as follows. In the second section, we discuss the underlying theoretical background. In the third section, we develop our hypotheses. The research model depicted highlights the expected relationships with the antecedents and the outcome variables of entrepreneurial alertness. In the fourth section, we outline our methodological approach, and we discuss the results in the fifth; the discussion section that follows not only presents our conclusions but also details their implications and limitations, along with outlining future research avenues.

2. Theory

The entrepreneurship literature has long been characterized by a debate about whether opportunities are entrepreneurially discovered, which represents the view of the “individual/opportunity nexus” proposed by Shane and Venkataraman (Shane, 2012; Shane and Venkataraman, 2000), versus the creation view proposed by Alvarez and Barney (2007). The essence of entrepreneurship is the actions undertaken and the outcomes that result. As highlighted by Foss and Klein (2017), opportunities do not exist independently of human belief and action; they also require an entrepreneur to apply a creative process that leads to new firms, new products, or new markets. When entrepreneurs are successful, we can say that they have discovered an opportunity that others have missed. In this regard, we follow Kirzner’s (1999) view that entrepreneurial discovery is a metaphor. Following the middle path discussed in a dialogue between Foss and Klein (2017), we use the term “entrepreneurial discovery” as an exhaustive and exclusive way to distinguish successful entrepreneurs from successful non-entrepreneurs. We focus on successes to show a symmetry in the potential to exploit opportunities; the difference is that entrepreneurs are able to exploit entrepreneurial opportunities whereas non-entrepreneurs discover and respond to opportunities outside the entrepreneurship context (e.g., influencer, data scientists, technical program manager).

Referring to our focus on entrepreneurial alertness, we build on Kirzner’s (1973, 1999) cognition theory framework, in which alertness is defined as the skill of identifying entrepreneurial opportunities that have been overlooked by others. As such, our distinction between

entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs allows us to state that entrepreneurs have seen something that was overlooked by non-entrepreneurs. Integrating Kirzner’s early (1973) and later (1999) theory of alertness into McMullen and Shepherd’s (2006) development of entrepreneurial action offered additional insight into how entrepreneurial alertness interacts with and enhances the recognition of new opportunities. In the opportunity context, the concept of alertness can explain how entrepreneurial activities are revealed. Our study builds on this prior work and uses entrepreneurial emotions as antecedent variables of entrepreneurial alertness to discovery. Thus, entrepreneurial discovery works as an outcome variable in our study in such a way that entrepreneurs who have successfully discovered an opportunity are defined as entrepreneurs in our study. Successful non-entrepreneurs are defined as any other individuals who have also successfully discovered an opportunity but outside the entrepreneurial context. The success of both entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs has been recognized by leading publications such as Forbes.

As a fundamental step, Kirzner’s alertness theory posits a difference in cognitive characteristics between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs. Their cognition shows different attention levels for specific information and patterns for evaluating potential business opportunities with profit potential. Behavioral and cognitive factors allow us to shape values and beliefs that might use alertness to trigger actions that are important for new venture creation. Pattern recognition may play a role in entrepreneurial alertness (Baron, 2006). What leads to entrepreneurial alertness is the cognitive capacity to recognize that one situation is like another in a meaningful way. Abstract knowledge structures in our cognitive systems such as schemata or patterns come into play (Valliere, 2013). For instance, previous research has treated individuals as “cognitive misers” who are able to use and connect information quickly to judge potential opportunities (Taylor, 1981; Dutta and Crossan, 2005). Recognizing patterns represents an individual’s ability to develop insights that can identify an entrepreneurial opportunity in a complex and uncertain world. In this regard, inspiration and imagination might be entrepreneurial cognitive guides in recognizing the value of information, a skill that non-entrepreneurs have not yet developed (Reed, 2004; Yu, 2001). Furthermore, entrepreneurs possess the cognitive ability to envision the future (Kirzner, 1985) clearly enough to make them confident about taking risks. This phenomenon shows similarities to signal detection theory (Swets, 1992), which suggests that the better an entrepreneur’s cognitive ability in sensing information (whether or not emotions are involved), the greater the possibility of discovering a successful entrepreneurial opportunity (Tang et al., 2012). Along this line of argument, actively entrepreneurial individuals show signs of success, such as being listed as successful entrepreneurs, that provide enough evidence of possessing those essential cognitive abilities. Thus, in our study we compare successful entrepreneurs with successful non-entrepreneurs.

The importance of different emotions in entrepreneurship across different stages has been extensively discussed. More generally, a substantial body of evidence indicates that affect exerts a strong influence on cognition, which is the process through which information is entered into the memory, processed, and retrieved for later use (Forgas, 1995; Isen, 2002). Thus, we build on Kirzner’s cognitive theory (1973, 1999) and signal detection theory (Swets, 1992) and theorize that emotions stimulated by cognition influence entrepreneurs. In line with prior work, we categorize emotions as showing either positive or negative affect. While negative emotions reflect distress, anger, hostility, and nervousness, positive emotions reflect pleasure, such as being interested, excited, enthusiastic, and inspired (Watson et al., 1988). Positive affect can serve as a naturally occurring stimulus by boosting individuals’ perceptual fields and cognitive capacity (Foley and Bates, 2019). For instance, Shane et al. (2020) used brain scans to show that founders’ passion—a deeply intense positive emotion—raises informal investors’ interest in financing new ventures. The passion contagion process and individual entrepreneurial passion are crucial success factors in

acquiring entrepreneurial finance (Li et al., 2017). Furthermore, Davis et al. (2017) provide evidence that the indirect influence of a product's perceived creativity is heightened when funders perceive the lead entrepreneur as passionate. In a longitudinal study conducted more than a decade ago, Baum and Locke (2004) found that, among other factors, a well-communicated vision had direct impacts on venture growth and mediated the effects of passion, tenacity, and new resource skill on subsequent growth. Su et al. (2020) stressed that entrepreneurs' positive emotions make them resilient in complex and uncertain business environments. This positivity promotes the formation of entrepreneurial intention through intuitive and analytical cognitive processing to encourage entrepreneurial resources. Thus, emotional return represents a performance indicator alongside economic return. To conclude, it seems not only possible but also plausible that positive affect strengthens entrepreneurial alertness for entrepreneurial discovery, but research has thus far been inconclusive as to how negative affect interacts with entrepreneurial alertness for entrepreneurial discovery. Our study contributes to the literature by providing a balanced viewpoint on both positive and negative affect.

3. Hypothesis development

3.1. Entrepreneurial alertness as antecedent and outcome

Entrepreneurial activities are exceptionally challenging human endeavors. Although the research field of entrepreneurship has shown continuous momentum since Schumpeter first theorized on the topic (1934, 1942), little is known about the role of emotions and alertness in the nonlinear, complex, and iterative discovery of entrepreneurial opportunities. Previous studies provide evidence that factors related to cognition influence entrepreneurial processes (Baron, 2007; FooDer, 2011; Welpe et al., 2012). In line with existing research, we use the expression "emotions" as a broad label that includes different types of subjective feelings (Cardon et al., 2012). Emotions vary in their arousal and valence. For instance, some are powerful but short-lived responses to specific stimuli; others are less powerful, diffuse, and comparatively permanent reactions to general stimuli. In this study, we also build on Cardon et al.'s (2012) definition of emotions: "Entrepreneurial emotion refers to the affect, emotions, moods, and/or feelings—of individuals or a collective—that are antecedent to, concurrent with, and/or a consequence of the entrepreneurial process, meaning the recognition/creation, evaluation, reformulation, and/or the exploitation of a possible opportunity" (p. 3).

Individuals tend to use emotions in decision making, positive or negative affect (Dane and Pratt, 2007); because emotions shape the processing of information, they tend to influence individuals' assessments (Welppe et al., 2012). Consistent with Baron's (2007) assertion, FooDer (2011) provides evidence that emotions concurrently affect entrepreneurs' evaluation of opportunities. Although previous contributions have yielded helpful insights into the interplay of emotions and opportunity evaluation (Cardon et al., 2012, 2013, 2017; Chen et al., 2009), scholars have thus far failed to explain how positive and negative emotions affect levels of entrepreneurial alertness to potential business opportunities. Moreover, we assume that the influence of different emotions on alertness levels and discovery differ between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs; however, no evidence has yet been provided on this point. Overall, contemporary studies fail to evaluate the impact of different (levels of) emotions on entrepreneurial alertness by considering both entrepreneurs' and non-entrepreneurs' perspectives using comprehensive within-group variations. In this regard, we follow Baron and Tang's (2011) call for research related to these relationships in entrepreneurship, which can generate profound explanations of how cognitive processes are shaped and how they can be trained among (non-)entrepreneurs.

Entrepreneurial alertness is vital to identifying new opportunities (Baron, 2007). In Kirzner's (1973, 1979) cognition theory framework,

alertness is defined as the skill of identifying entrepreneurial opportunities that are overlooked by others. Building on that theory, Tang et al. (2012) expanded McMullen and Shepherd's (2006) work by refining the alertness definition with three distinct elements: scanning and searching for information, connecting previously disparate information, and evaluating business opportunities. Tang et al.'s (2012) alertness scale explores antecedent and outcome variables. Specifically, we follow Tang et al.'s (2012) recommendations for investigating insights regarding entrepreneurial processes by studying entrepreneurial emotions as antecedent variables of entrepreneurial alertness.

It has been argued that affect plays a role in entrepreneurial opportunity recognition (Baron, 2008). Alertness prepares people to be ready to do something, and emotions (positive or negative) can trigger that alertness. In the present framework, we build on work regarding Kirzner's cognitive theory (1973, 1999) and signal detection theory (Swets, 1992), which proposes that emotions can act as signals to draw individuals' attention to certain stimuli (e.g., Ellsworth and Scherer, 2003). While some scholars argue that negative emotion triggers greater alertness, others argue that positive emotions trigger entrepreneurial activities. For instance, prior research shows that dissatisfaction leads to discovery (Herron and Sapienza, 1992; Zhou, 2008). By contrast, Levasseur et al. (2022) highlight that positive affect has a positive impact on entrepreneurial alertness, with evaluation and judgment both positively impacting incremental firm innovation. We differentiate between positive affect and negative affect and consider them simultaneously because emotions can trigger alertness, consciously or unconsciously, as posited by cognitive theory (Kirzner, 1973, 1999) and signal detection theory (Swets, 1992). Moreover, Baumeister et al.'s (2007) theory of emotion stresses emotions as a feedback system, so that the emotions experienced can provide compelling information. Affect priming theory suggests a supplementary clarification of the impact of emotions on perceptions; it proposes that emotions stimulate associations and memories (Bower and Forgas, 2001), which shape assessments (Baron, 2007). For instance, when individuals are in a positive (negative) emotional state, positive (negative) associations or memories are stimulated (Bower, 1991; Clore and Tamir, 2002). In other words, entrepreneurial emotions can drive alertness and vice versa. In this regard, different levels of emotions might be entrepreneurial cognitive guides in recognizing the value of information, which are expected to distinguish entrepreneurs from non-entrepreneurs (Reed, 2004; Yu, 2001). Thus, we propose the following:

Hypothesis 1a. Positive and negative affect drive entrepreneurial alertness differently.

Hypothesis 1b. Entrepreneurs' and non-entrepreneurs' positive and negative affect are different.

Lanivich et al.'s (2022) investigation of the concept of entrepreneurial alertness reveals inconsistencies and emerging trends in the field. Entrepreneurial alertness contributes to cognition-based theories regarding opportunities by representing a specific cognitive ability of entrepreneurs—in contrast to non-entrepreneurs—to sense entrepreneurial ideas. Kirzner's alertness theory centers on behavioral and cognitive factors to highlight that entrepreneurial alertness shapes values and beliefs that enable seeing or sensing patterns and specific information that are useful for evaluating potential business opportunities. Pattern recognition has been reported to play an important role in alertness levels (Baron, 2006), which shape the cognitive capacity to recognize and envision the future (Valliere, 2013). Recognizing patterns represents an individual's ability to develop insights that identify entrepreneurial opportunities in a complex and uncertain world. In this regard, also recognizing and sensing that inspiration and imagination might be entrepreneurial cognitive guides is a skill that non-entrepreneurs have not yet developed (Yu, 2001; Reed, 2004). Entrepreneurs possess the cognitive ability to envision the future (Kirzner, 1985) clearly enough to make them confident about taking risks. This phenomenon shows similarities to signal detection theory

(Swets, 1992), which suggests that the better an entrepreneur's cognitive ability to sense information, the higher the possibility of discovering a successful entrepreneurial opportunity (Tang et al., 2012). Along this line of argument, actively entrepreneurial individuals show signs of entrepreneurial success, such as being listed as successful entrepreneurs.

While some scholars argue that discovery is linked to information equilibrium in the market (Foss and Klein, 2009), others insist that an entrepreneurial opportunity can be either created over time and/or discovered (Alvarez and Barney, 2007). Overall, to exploit opportunities, individuals must recognize and discover them (Vaghely and Julien, 2010). Consequently, the identification and recognition of entrepreneurial opportunities are correlated, with both creativity and alertness playing a role (Ardichvili et al., 2003). Alertness affects the discovery of an entrepreneurial idea and the exploitation of an entrepreneurial opportunity (Lumpkin and Lichtenstein, 2005; Valliere, 2013). The discovery of new business opportunities reinforces some entrepreneurs' positive mindset, which makes them more alert to their surroundings. This relationship is stronger among entrepreneurs than non-entrepreneurs since the former have more exposure to such experiences and the reinforcement is stronger. Thus, based on this line of argument, we offer the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 2a. Entrepreneurial alertness facilitates entrepreneurial discovery.

3.2. Differences between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs

The process of creativity affects the alertness levels (Ardichvili et al., 2003). A creative process starts with a prepared person who is experienced in decision making to solve problems. The individual creates new mental connotations; the more novel the mental situations, the greater the chance of creativity that results from divergent thinking (Gielnik et al., 2014). Consequently, creativity can facilitate alertness. In this framework, the evaluation of information influences this process (Shane et al., 2000; Gielnik et al., 2014). While linking information contributes to alertness, its level also depends on an individual's subjectivity, which mediates the discovery process. Alertness arises when an individual observes and evaluates an idea, which is subjective and thus influenced by knowledge, sharing that knowledge with peers, and the final assessment (Gielnik et al., 2014). Therefore, entrepreneurs' evaluations of opportunities are expected to differ from those of non-entrepreneurs.

We build on Kirzner's (1973, 1999) cognition theory framework, in which alertness is defined as the skill of identifying entrepreneurial opportunities overlooked by others. Integrating Kirzner's early (1973) and later (1999) theory of alertness with McMullen and Shepherd's (2006) recent development of entrepreneurial action explains how entrepreneurial alertness engages with and enhances the recognition of new opportunities. In the opportunity context, the concept of alertness can explain how entrepreneurial activities are uncovered. Kirzner's alertness theory posits the existence of different cognitive characteristics between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs. Their cognition shows different attention levels for specific information and patterns to see business opportunities with profit potential. Opportunity assessment is also influenced by subjective fear of failure and an individual's vulnerability (Mitchell and Shepherd, 2010). Thus, in this context, risk perception, which differs between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs, is expected to play a role, as previous research has emphasized (e.g., Keh, 2002). Anticipated financial returns also impact the assessment of business opportunities (Shepherd and DeTienne, 2005; Welpel et al., 2012), another element that may differ between profit-seeking entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs. Shepherd and DeTienne (2005) explain that the higher the potential return, the greater the number of recognized opportunities. Behavioral and cognitive factors allow us to shape values and beliefs that might use alertness to trigger actions that are important for new venture evaluation and creation. Based on Baron's (2006) pattern recognition work, we expect that

entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs exhibit different pattern recognition skills, and thus show different alertness levels. As a final step, entrepreneurial discovery works as a dependent variable in such a way that entrepreneurs who have successfully discovered an opportunity are assumed to exhibit different levels of entrepreneurial discovery than successful non-entrepreneurs who have also successfully discovered an opportunity but outside the entrepreneurial context. Therefore, we offer the following hypotheses:

Hypothesis 2b. Entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs exhibit different levels of alertness.

Hypothesis 2c. Entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs discover opportunities differently.

4. Methods

4.1. Ethical information

Our research complies with all relevant ethical regulations. This study has been reviewed and approved by the ethics committee of the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich (German: Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich, ETH Zürich, number 2021-N-168) and by Harvard University's Committee on the Use of Human Subjects, which serves as the university-wide institutional review board (IRB; number IRB18-0203). Study 2 was also reviewed by Harvard's IRB and determined not to involve human subject research as defined by Department of Health and Human Services regulations; as such, no additional review is required. Electronic informed consent was obtained from all participants in Study 1. In line with ethical standards for fair pay for online labor (Berg et al., 2018; Engels, 2021), subjects in Study 1 received USD 10 as an incentive for their participation, which took an average of 20 min. Hereby, with regard to Study 2 we would like to stress that as a comparative study between non-entrepreneurs and entrepreneurs we do not judge one's Twitter posts on an individual level nor do we correlate it to one's individual personality. Thus, we have anonymized the analyzed Twitter users. All study materials, data, and analysis code have been deposited on the Open Science Framework (OSF) at <https://osf.io/f9sjm/>. All material, data, and code are available at an anonymous link: https://osf.io/f9sjm/?view_only=b2ba82f6b7da42b08645ffe1b767ffc3.

4.2. Design overview

We conducted two complementary studies to answer our research question. Study 1 focuses on a survey-based investigation to examine our core idea that entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs display different levels of entrepreneurial alertness and discovery, also investigating its linear relationship, while Study 2 focuses on an observation of Twitter accounts from successful entrepreneurs versus successful non-entrepreneurs to observe and compare their use of positive and negative words in tweets. The advantage of this approach is that we first explore the nature of relationships via the survey and then test the underlying assumption about positive and negative traits expressed over a long period of time through publicly available statements by successful entrepreneurs and successful non-entrepreneurs. Moreover, the expected different levels of affect between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs inspired, for purposes of replication, field Study 2 to explore whether the self-reported levels of emotions are also demonstrated by entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs when sharing emotional content on a public platform. This methodological approach enables us to rule out reverse causality, which means that alertness represents a mediator between positive affect and discovery because successful entrepreneurs have successfully employed those tools. The two studies' methodologies are discussed below.

4.3. Study 1

Data collection ran from April 17 to May 1, 2018, in the United States; 75% of survey participants were U.S. citizens. The other 25 subjects indicated the following nationalities: eight from India, three each from Canada and China, two each from Nigeria and Turkey, and one each from Brazil, Cameroon, Lesotho, Nigeria, Turkey, Uganda, and Yemen. Harvard's Decision Science Lab was fully responsible for administering the survey. The lab advertised the study to its subject pool of registered members, who were screened for quality on a regular basis. The participants who were invited came to the physical Decision Science Lab, where they completed the survey and received their incentives immediately afterward. We targeted 100 participants overall, with approximately equal proportions of entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs. As soon as this numerical objective was reached, we stopped data collection. Although all our survey questions were mandatory, nine submissions had missing data on our core constructs and were thus excluded from analysis. That left us with 91 online questionnaires completed by 54 non-entrepreneurs (27 men and 27 women) and 37 entrepreneurs (25 men and 12 women). The 39 women and 52 men ranged between 18 and 69 years old. Regarding education, 23% possessed a high school degree or equivalent, 8% an associate degree or equivalent, 43% a bachelor's degree or equivalent, 23% a master's degree or equivalent, and 3% a doctorate or equivalent.

4.3.1. Measurements and analysis

Entrepreneurs versus non-entrepreneurs. To nuance and contrast entrepreneur and non-entrepreneurs in this work, we adapt the definition used by Koudstaal et al. (2016): an entrepreneur is someone who founded and is running a small business and still owns 100% of the shares. On the contrary, in line with this definition, a non-entrepreneur is thus someone who did not found and is not running a small business and does not own any shares of such a business. For Study 2, *Forbes* includes entrepreneurs in their Next1000 list based on whether they are "sole proprietors, self-funded shops and pre-revenue startups in every region of the country—all with under \$10 million in revenue." We are of the opinion that those two definitions are not in conflict because both put a single founding individual at the center and limit revenue, creating a ceiling that excludes who were aiming at an initial public offering or private equity deals to speed firm growth.

There were two Study 1 surveys, one for entrepreneurs and one for non-entrepreneurs; both were administered by Harvard's Decision Science Lab. The lab's participant pool used pre-screening to send the correct survey to either entrepreneurs or non-entrepreneurs. An additional question regarding self-categorization of stakeholder type was added to act as an additional quality check in both surveys: "How do you see yourself? (1) Entrepreneur: you are self-employed, meaning you run any kind of business; (2) Financier: you have invested your own or others' money (more than 1 USD) in a business (e.g. crowdsourcing, friend's potential business idea); (3) Researcher: you do research for living, fun, or as a time-part job; (4) Student in a policymaking area." Our subjects are two separate representative groups into which individuals assigned themselves. Thus, entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs in this study belong to mutually exclusive groups.

Independent and dependent variables. To examine the research question, we used several data analysis methods in multiple waves. To inspect entrepreneur-related differences, we used a number of measurements. We applied Tang et al.'s (2012) scale of entrepreneurial alertness, which includes scanning and search, association, connection, and evaluation and judgment of opportunities. Following Davidsson (2003), we define discovery as the conceptual side of new venture development, from initial idea to fully worked-out business concept. In line with this definition, we used Farmer et al.'s (2011) well-established scale to measure entrepreneurial discovery. For positive and negative mood effects, we employed the 10-item mood scales that comprise the PANAS developed by Watson et al. (1988). The participants were

instructed as follows: "This scale consists of a number of words that describe different feelings and emotions. Read each item and then mark the appropriate answer in the space next to that word. Indicate to what extent you generally feel this way; that is, how you feel on the average. Use the following scale to record your answers." Participants answered from "very slightly or not at all" (1) to "extremely" (5). Based on these questions, "excited" and "enthusiastic" and "upset" and "jittery," for example, represent stable feelings over time. We applied self-report measure to assess two broad domains of affect, namely positive affect and negative affect. The former is associated with pleasurable engagement with the environment, whereas the latter reflects a dimension of general distress summarizing a variety of negative states like anger, guilt, and anxiety. The PANAS is suitable for both measuring state and trait affectivity. Its brevity and frequently demonstrated psychometric properties (e.g., Crawford and Henry, 2004; Leue and Lange, 2011) have contributed to its widespread use in many areas of psychology.

We employed several multivariate methods, such as ANOVA, Mann-Whitney U tests, and linear mixed-effect models, along with Bayesian analysis of those approaches. Before conducting an in-depth data examination, we performed several tests, as suggested by Podsakoff et al. (2003), to assess the quality of the data gathered. We conducted an exploratory factor analysis. The measurements were suitable because all variables attained very good values of more than 0.5 for all items (Kaiser, 1974) on the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KOM) tests (Dziuban and Shirkey, 1974). Furthermore, all determinants of the constructs' correlation matrix were greater than the necessary value of 0.00001, and none of the communalities was less than 0.5. On the whole, the total variance was well described, according to existing research (Hair et al., 1995; Lattin et al., 2003). Cronbach's alpha was above 0.90 for all variables. Consequently, the validity and reliability of the applied construct were adequate in this study. As all variance inflation factors were below the commonly accepted multicollinearity threshold of three, there was no multicollinearity in the model (Hair et al., 2006). Table 1 outlines items under investigation, including survey questions, Cronbach's alpha, determinant, the KMO test results, means, standard deviations, and communalities.

Control variables. Scholars have recently provided conflicting evidence regarding whether there is a significant gender difference in discovering entrepreneurial opportunities. For instance, earlier research showed that alertness does not depend on an entrepreneur's gender (Tang et al., 2012). However, other research has insisted that gender and culture affect various aspects of entrepreneurship, such as entrepreneurial potential (Ward et al., 2019) and motivation (Carter et al., 2003). By contrast, Maes et al. (2014) showed that social norms have no statistically significant impact on entrepreneurial intentions. A review paper presented by Sullivan and Meek (2012) reported that women's social networks relate to their identification of opportunities (Greve and Salaff, 2003; Harrison and Mason, 2007) and that women's prior work and life experiences differ from men, which is relevant to their opportunity recognition and the types of opportunities they pursue (DeTienne and Chandler, 2007). As that paper concludes, women's opportunity recognition patterns differ from men. Furthermore, other individual factors like self-efficacy, persistence, and the need for achievement combine with situational factors like government policies, work field environment, and family background to play a significant role in entrepreneurial intentions. Thus, in this study, gender, nationality, work experience, educational level, and age of the individual constitute the control variables. According to an analysis of variance (ANOVA), the two groups (entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs) were not statistically significant different for all control variables. Table 2 presents those results.

Table 3 presents the construct means, standard deviations, and correlations for Study 1. On average, participants were approximately 30.23 years old and had 9.14 years of work experience. Seventy-five percent of the 91 survey participants were U.S. citizens. After excluding nine subjects due to missing data, 39 women and 52 men

Table 1
Measurements for study 1.

Entrepreneurial Alertness (N = 91) (Cronbach's alpha = 0.910. Determinant = 0.0000437. KMO = 0.862***)	Mean	SD	Communalities		
<i>"Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:"</i>					
The participants have been instructed as follows:					
I have frequent interactions with others to acquire new information.	5.64	1.243	0.523		
I always keep an eye out for new business ideas when looking for information.	4.66	1.893	0.640		
I read news, magazines, or trade publications regularly to acquire new information.	4.75	2.122	0.613		
I browse the Internet every day.	6.38	1.218	0.711		
I am an avid information seeker.	5.88	1.452	0.807		
I am always actively looking for new information.	5.80	1.529	0.860		
I see links between seemingly unrelated pieces of information.	5.45	1.310	0.820		
I am good at "connecting dots."	5.66	1.293	0.884		
I often see connections between previously unconnected domains of information.	5.48	1.294	0.908		
I have a gut feeling for potential opportunities.	4.76	1.573	0.652		
I can distinguish between profitable opportunities and not-so-profitable opportunities.	4.32	1.646	0.783		
I have a knack for telling high-value opportunities apart from low-value opportunities.	4.24	1.662	0.772		
When facing multiple opportunities, I am able to select the good ones.	4.90	1.334	0.692		
Entrepreneurial Discovery (N = 91) (Cronbach's alpha = 0.964. Determinant = 0.0000157. KMO = 0.930***)	Mean	SD	Communalities		
<i>"Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:"</i>					
The participants have been instructed as follows:					
I am engaged in a deliberate, systematic search for new business ideas.	3.75	2.036	0.664		
I am thinking about a number of business ideas that can potentially grow into a real business.	4.20	2.018	0.720		
I discuss potential ideas for a new business with my friends and family.	4.26	2.065	0.724		
I talk about potential ideas with people that I have a business or working relationship with.	4.10	2.103	0.824		
I discuss with people other than those mentioned above with regard to potential business ideas.	3.60	2.049	0.702		
I have taken or will take some classes or seminars on how to start a new business.	3.99	2.219	0.728		
I (alone or with others) will define potential ideas further for products or services.	4.14	2.127	0.879		
I (alone or with others) will try to define further the market opportunity for potential ideas.	3.99	2.121	0.893		
I will devote further time to potential ideas for business.	4.31	2.048	0.863		
Positive Affect (Cronbach's alpha = 0.898. Determinant = 0.005. KMO = 0.893***)	Mean	SD	Negative Affect (Cronbach's alpha = 0.893. Determinant = 0.006. KMO = 0.875***)	Mean	SD
The participants have been instructed as follows: "This scale consists of a number of words that describe different feelings and emotions. Read each item and then mark the appropriate answer in the space next to that word. Indicate to what extent you generally feel this way; that is, how you feel on the average. Use the following scale to record your answers."					
interested	4.03	0.809	distressed	2.13	0.980
excited	3.45	0.922	upset	1.85	0.918
strong	3.55	0.934	guilty	1.89	0.960
enthusiastic	3.70	1.038	scared	1.69	0.741
proud	3.37	1.161	hostile	1.48	0.794
alert	3.56	0.945	irritable	1.97	0.960
inspired	3.66	1.077	ashamed	1.58	0.817
determined	3.93	0.879	nervous	2.34	1.067
active	3.70	1.038	jittery	1.99	0.994
attentive	3.92	0.934	afraid	1.69	0.852

Table 2
Descriptive statistics across groups including ANOVA in Study 1.

		N	Mean	SD	F statistic	p-value
Non-entrepreneur	Gender	54	0.50	0.504	$F(1,89) = 2.791$	0.098
Entrepreneur		37	0.32	0.474		
Non-entrepreneur	Age	54	28.65	11.212	$F(1,89) = 2.313$	0.132
Entrepreneur		37	32.54	13.055		
Non-entrepreneur	Education	54	2.76	1.228	$F(1,89) = 0.00$	0.992
Entrepreneur		37	2.76	1.038		
Non-entrepreneur	Work experience	54	7.67	9.825	$F(1,89) = 2.511$	0.117
Entrepreneur		37	11.30	11.953		
Non-entrepreneur	Nationality	54	163.35	53.388	$F(1,89) = 0.057$	0.811
Entrepreneur		37	160.70	49.570		

Note on operationalization: Entrepreneur (1) versus Non-entrepreneur (0); Women (1) versus men (0); Age in years, Education as follows: High school degree (1), Associate degree or equivalent (2), Bachelor's degree or equivalent (3), Master's degree or equivalent (4), Doctorate or equivalent (5); Work experience in years; Nationality according to country codes.

participated in this study, but the gender proportions differed in the two groups: 54 individuals were non-entrepreneurs (27 men, 27 women), and 37 were entrepreneurs (25 men, 12 women).

Table 4 outlines the descriptive statistics for entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs to stress the differences in positive and negative affect, entrepreneurial alertness levels, and entrepreneurial discovery. All the means of the variables, with the exception of negative affect, tended to

be higher for entrepreneurs. The lower levels of negative affect of entrepreneurs inspired, for purposes of replication, field Study 2 to explore whether these self-reported lower levels of negative emotion are also demonstrated by entrepreneurs when sharing emotional content on a public platform.

Table 3
Study 1: Construct means, standard deviations and correlations.

	<i>N</i> = 91	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	Entrepreneur or Non-Entrepreneur	0.41	0.494	1							
2	Gender	0.43	0.498	-0.174	1						
3	Age	30.23	12.079	0.159	-0.076	1					
4	Work Experience	9.14	10.826	0.166	0.055	.775**	1				
5	Positive Affect	3.69	0.706	0.058	-0.015	0.139	0.180	1			
6	Negative Affect	1.86	0.651	-0.058	-0.199	-0.194	-.300**	-.367**	1		
7	Entrepreneurial Alertness	5.22	1.060	.372**	-0.105	0.128	.305**	.474**	-.252*	1	
8	Entrepreneurial Discovery	4.04	1.839	.495**	-0.127	0.124	.227*	.418**	-0.129	.725**	1

Notes: Significance codes: **= $p < .01$, * = $p < .05$. Operationalization: Entrepreneur (1) versus Non-entrepreneur (0); Women (1) versus men (0); Age in years, Work experience in years. Composite measures: positive affect; negative affect; entrepreneurial alertness; entrepreneurial discovery.

Table 4
Study 1: Descriptive statistics across groups.

<i>N</i> _{Entrepreneur} = 37 <i>N</i> _{Non-Entrepreneur} = 54		Mean	SD	SE	Mean difference
Positive Affect	Non-Entrepreneur	3.66	0.65	0.09	-0.08
	Entrepreneur	3.74	0.79	0.13	
Negative Affect	Non-Entrepreneur	1.89	0.59	0.08	0.08
	Entrepreneur	1.82	0.74	0.12	
Entrepreneurial Alertness	Non-Entrepreneur	4.90	1.09	0.15	-0.80
	Entrepreneur	5.70	0.83	0.14	
Entrepreneurial Discovery	Non-Entrepreneur	3.29	1.76	0.24	-1.84
	Entrepreneur	5.13	1.35	0.22	

4.4. Study 2

To enrich our cross-sectional research design of Study 1, we measured emotions over time in posts on Twitter to investigate particularly whether the emotion constructs are malleable or time-varying. In order to analyze whether entrepreneurs tend to tweet more positively than non-entrepreneurs, a Python program was written to retrieve tweets from the Twitter accounts of 185 entrepreneurs and 264 non-entrepreneurs via an application programming interface (API) to determine the sentimental value of the text, using a file containing 1916 positive and 2292 negative keywords from the Harvard IV-4 dictionary.² The entrepreneurs appear on a leading public list of successful entrepreneurs (<https://www.forbes.com/next1000/>), while the successful non-entrepreneurs were drawn from a leading public list of successful non-entrepreneurs (<https://www.forbes.com/30-under-30/directory/>). Subjects were collected where a Twitter handle was available. To minimize potential selection bias and increase external validity, we randomly selected individuals one after the other and checked to see if the individual had a Twitter account that could be used for our panel data set. Not all entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs had an identifiable Twitter account. We chose *Forbes'* directory under 30 because they are more likely to be Twitter users. Furthermore, we had an average age of 30.79 years in Study 1.

Compared to Study 1 in this study we analyzed only successful entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs to provide a way to distinguish entrepreneurs from non-entrepreneurs in our study; while there is symmetry in opportunities between the groups, there is a difference in whether those opportunities were entrepreneurial. For instance, this enabled us to assume that successful non-entrepreneurs also have an ability to envision and exploit opportunities, but not traditionally entrepreneurial ones. By focusing on successful individuals who

received a public ranking for their success in recognizing opportunities, we build a baseline in which the only differences between group are entrepreneurial versus non-entrepreneurial activities.

Positive and negative mood was measured using Twitter Streaming API and Twitter sentiment analysis using natural language processing with Python (<https://www.nltk.org/>; Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count). For this purpose, two scripts—data.py and sentiment.py—were coded (the code is available at <https://osf.io/f9sjm>). The data.py script is mainly responsible for retrieving the data from the Twitter API, using the Tweepy API wrapper. In this case, we searched through the timeline of entrepreneurial and non-entrepreneurial Twitter users and retrieved a so-called status object, which contains the data and metadata of each tweet. The data of the status object we explored consist of username, screen name, date created, text of tweet, hashtags, URLs, and user mentions. Furthermore, the program detects special characters like line breaks and checks whether a tweet is a retweet or a reply to another tweet, resulting in a clean text column that contains only the actual tweeted text. Once the text is cleaned up, every element is written to a csv file, where the matching columns were filled with the data we gathered.

The sentiment.py script helped us to draw a list of positive and negative keywords from the Harvard IV-4 dictionary Excel file, which were then used to determine whether the tweet was positive or negative; each such determination was gathered through the data.py script. First, the program retrieves all the keywords from the Excel file and saves them as a list data structure. It then checks how many positive and negative words each tweet has and calculates the positive and negative percentages for each tweet. Those values are filled in the previously created.csv file and used to determine whether a given user tweets more positively or negatively. Finally, the overall positive and negative values of each user are filled in to complete the.csv file.

Although Twitter now allows 280-word posts, we focused on 140-word tweets. This limitation allows for the unobtrusive observation of the behavior of individual people and the collection of time-sensitive information, providing an indication of people's emotional tendencies when broadcasting their words and is a precursor to the study of mood as trait, as revealed by the language used on social media. Such long-term observations, which are useful for measuring mood over an extended period, can otherwise be very difficult to capture.

Table 5 presents the means, standard deviations, and correlations on the subject level from the Twitter accounts of 185 entrepreneurs and 264 non-entrepreneurs (*N* = 449). Table 6 shows the Study 2 descriptive statistics from 28,478 tweets separated into entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs. Means, standard deviations, standard errors, and differences in means are reported for each group under investigation. We explored 15,160 tweets (53.2%) from 264 successful non-entrepreneurs and 13,318 tweets (46.8%) from 185 successful entrepreneurs.

5. Results

We have chosen to apply Bayesian inferences for the following key advantages (Bernardo and Smith, 2000; Robert, 2001; Wasserman,

² please delete this footnote

Table 5
Study 2: Means, standard deviations and correlations across groups (N = 449).

		Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Delta (Positive-Negative Words in %)	1.44	1.55	1					
2	Non-entrepreneurs (0) versus entrepreneurs (1)	0.41	0.49	-.144**	1				
3	Mean Amount of Tweets	32.21	22.61	0.053	-0.065	1			
4	Mean Words per Tweet	17.09	6.64	-.109*	.204**	-.146**	1		
5	Mean Likes per Tweet	1903.71	10193.06	-.098*	.205**	-.117*	.898**	1	
6	Mean Retweets	209.94	1371.20	.146**	.159**	-0.054	-.156**	-.128**	1

Notes: Significance codes: **= $p < .01$, * = $p < .05$.

Table 6
Study 2: Descriptive statistics of entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs.

	Group	Mean	SD	SE	Difference in Mean
Difference in word usage: positive minus negative, in % of tweeted words	Non-entrepreneurs	1.253	1.602	0.099	
	Entrepreneurs	1.712	1.436	0.106	0.459
Mean of positive words per tweet (in %)	Non-entrepreneurs	2.084	1.486	0.091	
	Entrepreneurs	2.345	1.345	0.099	0.261
Mean of negative words per tweet (in %)	Non-entrepreneurs	0.831	0.784	0.048	
	Entrepreneurs	0.633	0.587	0.043	-0.198
Mean of amount of tweets	Non-entrepreneurs	29.212	21.277	1.31	
	Entrepreneurs	36.495	23.789	1.749	7.283
Mean words per tweet	Non-entrepreneurs	17.39	7.279	0.448	
	Entrepreneurs	16.665	5.584	0.411	-0.725
Mean likes per tweet	Non-entrepreneurs	3233.84	13140.49	808.741	
	Entrepreneurs	5.575	17.067	1.255	-3228.265
Mean retweets	Non-entrepreneurs	356.489	1774.945	109.24	
	Entrepreneurs	0.81	1.794	0.132	-355.679
Amount of tweets	Non-entrepreneurs	57.424	42.554	2.619	
	Entrepreneurs	71.989	47.577	3.498	14.565

Notes. Non-entrepreneurs (N = 264), Entrepreneurs (N = 185), Standard deviation (SD), Standard error (SE).

2004): (1) multiple testing does not matter in the Bayesian approach (Dienes, 2011); (2) its ability to generate estimates and credible intervals for any derived parameter or predicted variable directly computed from the posterior distribution; (3) it yields more powerful estimates of between-subject effects than traditional null hypothesis significance testing because that approach uses different and larger-denominator error terms when computing *F* ratios for between-subject effects than for within-subject effects, whereas Bayesian estimation finds parameter values that are jointly credible (Kruschke, 2014); and (4) the use of methods to calculate support in favor of—and not only against—the null hypothesis enables us to get the most out of our results (Rouder and Morey, 2012; Dienes, 2014). Thus, although we receive null results, we are able to draw conclusions by using them as evidence for a zero effect.

We performed the analysis with both SPSS v. 28 and JSAP v. 0.16.2.0 using default effect size priors (Cauchy scale 0.707). As recommended (Gelman et al., 2008) in cases where there is little existing knowledge about a topic, we use broad default non-informative priors for all coefficients to reflect the absence of previous knowledge of these parameters' distributions and to ensure minimal influence on the form of the posterior distributions (Kruschke, 2013, 2014). Results are reported using two-tailed BFs with BF_{10} when we found a difference and BF_{01} where we found no difference. Effect size estimates are reported as median posterior Cohen's *d* with 95% credibility intervals.

5.1. Study 1

Table 7 presents the results of the (Bayesian) Mann-Whitney *U* test and linear mixed-effect model for the hypotheses under investigation. H1a suggests that positive and negative affect drive entrepreneurial alertness differently. The fixed-effects estimates of the linear mixed-effect model show that while negative affect does not significantly influence entrepreneurial alertness, positive effect does. Thus, alternative H1a was only partially supported; specifically, while positive mood was positively related to entrepreneurial alertness ($\beta = 0.714$, $SE = 0.23$, $p = .035$, $t = 3.1$, $F(1,4.07) = 9.607$), negative affect was negatively related to entrepreneurial alertness ($\beta = -0.098$, $SE = 0.183$, $p = .614$, $t = -0.535$, $F(1,5.54) = 0.286$). Overall, it can be concluded that individuals with positive emotions tend to be more alert, while negative emotions do not predict any particular level of alertness.

H1b suggests that entrepreneurs' and non-entrepreneurs' positive and negative affect are different. Because significant results of a Shapiro-Wilk test suggest a deviation from normality, traditional Mann-Whitney *U* tests and their Bayesian versions are reported. We found moderate evidence that entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs do not self-report different levels of positive ($M_{difference} = 0.08$, $BF_{01} = 3.293$, $W = 906$, $p = .454$) or negative affect ($M_{difference} = -0.08$, $BF_{01} = 3.291$, $W = 1124.5$, $p = .311$). We can conclude that entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs do not differ in their positive and negative emotionally expressed traits.

H2a, which proposes that entrepreneurial alertness is positively related to entrepreneurial discovery, was also supported ($\beta = 1.129$, $SE = 0.142$, $t = 7.959$, $p = .012$, $F(1,2.19) = 63.348$). Because significant results of a Shapiro-Wilk test suggest a deviation from normality, traditional Mann-Whitney *U* tests and their Bayesian versions are reported for H2b and H2c. We found statistically significant strong evidence for H2b, which holds that entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs have different levels of alertness ($M_{difference} = -0.80$, $BF_{10} = 18.138$, $W = 572$, $p = .0005648$). As expected, entrepreneurs show significantly higher levels of entrepreneurial alertness. Finally, we also found extremely strong support for H2c, which proposes that entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs discover entrepreneurial opportunities differently ($M_{difference} = -1.84$, $BF_{10} = 870.674$, $W = 420$, $p = .00000291$). As expected, entrepreneurs show significantly higher levels of entrepreneurial discovery. The results from H1a to H2c support the mediating effects of entrepreneurial alertness in the relationship between emotions and entrepreneurial discovery among entrepreneurs. Table 7

Table 7
Study 1: Results of the hypotheses.

Hypothesis 1a. Positive and negative affect drive entrepreneurial alertness differently.

Fixed effects	Estimate	SE	df	t	p	df	F
Intercept	2.713	1.255	3.838	2.161	0.1		
Positive affect	0.714	0.23	4.069	3.1	0.035*	1, 4.07	9.607
Negative affect	-0.098	0.183	5.536	-0.535	0.614	1, 5.54	0.286

Hypothesis 1b. Entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs' positive and negative affect are different.

(Bayesian) Mann-Whitney U Test statistics including descriptive statistics						95% CI for Hodges-Lehmann Estimate		
	BF ₁₀	W	Rhat	W	p	Hodges-Lehmann Estimate	Lower	Upper
Positive affect	3.293	906	1	906	0.454	-0.1	-0.4	0.2
Negative affect	3.291	1124.5	1.012	1125	0.311	0.1	-0.1	0.4

Hypothesis 2a. Entrepreneurial alertness facilitates entrepreneurial discovery.

Fixed effects	Estimate	SE	df	t	p	df	F
Intercept	-1.804	0.676	8.857	-2.67	0.026		
Alertness	1.129	0.142	2.195	7.959	0.012*	1, 2.19	63.348

Hypothesis 2b. Entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs exhibit different levels of entrepreneurial alertness.

(Bayesian) Mann-Whitney U Test statistics including descriptive statistics						95% CI for Hodges-Lehmann Estimate		
	BF ₁₀	W	Rhat	W	p	Hodges-Lehmann Estimate	Lower	Upper
Alertness	18.138	572	1.02	572	0.0005648***	-0.769	-1.231	-0.385

Hypothesis 2c. Entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs discover opportunities differently.

(Bayesian) Mann-Whitney U Test statistics including descriptive statistics						95% CI for Hodges-Lehmann Estimate		
	BF ₁₀	W	Rhat	W	P	Hodges-Lehmann Estimate	Lower	Upper
Discovery	870.674	420	1.041	420	0.00000291***	-2	-2.778	-1.222

Note. Significance codes: *** = $p < .001$, ** = $p < .01$, * = $p < .05$. The intercept corresponds to the (unweighted) grand mean; for each factor with k levels, $k - 1$ parameters are estimated with sum contrast coding. Consequently, the estimates cannot be directly mapped to factor levels. Use estimated marginal means for obtaining estimates for each factor level/design cell or their differences. Model terms tested with Satterthwaite method. Stakeholder is used as a random effects grouping factor. Type III Sum of Squares. Standard errors (SE).

Note. Significance codes: ***= $p < .001$, ** = $p < .01$, * = $p < .05$. Significant results of a Shapiro-Wilk test suggests a deviation from normality. Thus, both Bayesian and Mann-Whitney U tests are reported.

Fig. 1. Shows how candidates in the two cohorts under investigation (successful entrepreneur and non-entrepreneur) entered and exited the panel dataset at separate points in time between 2009 and 2021, resulting in an unbalanced panel where entities are observed a different number of times. Although a balanced panel is ideal, this is not feasible with our research question, in that we are investigating successful entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs with publicly available Twitter accounts. However, due to the results of our chosen analytical approach—comparing overall average positive and negative word usage in percentage in Twitter tweets—the disadvantage of an unbalanced panel data did not affect our research results, as time does not matter for that comparison. When those individuals started their Twitter accounts at some point during the period does not affect our results, because Twitter’s popularity as an effective media tool grew over time. Fig. 1 demonstrates how the positive and negative word usage of entrepreneurs versus non-entrepreneurs evolved over time, although time itself is not our unit of analysis. Notes. A) Entrepreneurs’ sentiment rate of all tweets over time. B) Non-entrepreneurs’ sentiment rate of all tweets over time. Unbalanced panel data over time of non-entrepreneurs ($N = 264$) and entrepreneurs ($N = 185$) from 2009 to 2021.

summarizes the test statistics for each hypothesis; Fig. 1 illustrates the Bayesian analyses.

To conclude, as summarized in Fig. 2, we found moderate evidence in Study 1 that entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs show similar positive (BF₀₁ = 3.293 M = -0.158, 95% CI [-0.550, 0.227]) and negative

affect (BF₀₁ = 3.291 M = 0.151, 95% CI [-0.252, 0.562]). Furthermore, we found very strong evidence for significantly different levels for entrepreneurial alertness (BF₁₀ = 18.1379, M = -0.648, 95% CI [-1.072, -0.214]) and entrepreneurial discovery (BF₁₀ = 147, M = -0.828, 95% CI [-1.286, -0.387]). The levels between the two groups

Fig. 2. Study 1: Results of Bayesian analysis
Notes. JASP v. 0.16.2.0 with default effect size priors (Cauchy scale 0.707) have been used. Broad default non-informative priors for all coefficients have been used to reflect the absence of previous knowledge of these parameters' distributions and to have minimal influence on the form of the posterior distributions (Gelman et al., 2008; Kruschke, 2013, 2014). Results are reported using the two-tailed BF with BF₁₀ as we expect a difference. Effect size estimates are reported as median posterior Cohen's d with 95% credibility intervals.

were statistically significantly different. Additionally, all the means of the variables, with the exception of negative affect, tended to be higher for entrepreneurs.

5.2. Study 2

Because Study 1 showed that only positive affect drives entrepreneurial alertness, we conducted field Study 2 to investigate H1b—that entrepreneurs’ and non-entrepreneurs’ positive and negative affect are different—in greater depth. Using short messages on Twitter that reflect either a more positive or more negative word use tendency, we investigate whether entrepreneurs or non-entrepreneurs use positive or negative words more often in their tweets.

While words per tweet did not differ significantly between the two groups under investigation ($M_{\text{difference}} = 0.725$, $t_{\text{Welch}}(443.318) = 1.194$, $SE = 0.608$, 95% CI [-0.469, 1.92], $p = .233$, $d = 0.347$), both likes ($M_{\text{difference}} = -3228.265$, $t_{\text{Welch}}(263.001) = 3.992$, $SE = 808.74$, 95% CI [1635.832, 4820.699], $p = 8.514e^{-5}$) and retweets ($M_{\text{difference}} = -355.678$, $t_{\text{Welch}}(263.001) = 3.256$, $SE = 109.240$, 95% CI [140.581, 570.775], $p = .001$, $d = 0.283$) received by both entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs were significantly different, according to our t_{Welch} -tests. On average, non-entrepreneurs received 3234 likes and 356 retweets, while entrepreneurs received on average six likes and one retweet per tweet. Table 8 indicates that non-entrepreneurs used 2.08% positive words and 0.83% negative words in their tweets, on average, while entrepreneurs used 2.35% positive and 0.63% negative words in theirs. This leads to a significant difference in tweeting behavior, considering the delta of positive and negative words ($M_{\text{difference}} = -0.459$, $t_{\text{Welch}}(420.847) = -3.179$, $SE = 0.144$, 95% CI [-0.743, -0.175], $p = .002$, $d = -0.3$).

Because the Shapiro-Wilk test for normality revealed significant results ($W_{\text{Nonentrepreneur}} = 0.908$, $p = 1.168e^{-11}$, $W_{\text{Entrepreneur}} = 0.892$, $p = 1.525e^{-10}$) that suggest a deviation from normality and Levene’s test of

equality of variances was non-significant ($F(1) = 1.063$, $p = .303$), Table 8 outlines both the parametric Welch’s and non-parametric Mann-Whitney test results. Both show that entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs are significantly different across different word use in their tweets: $t_{\text{Welch}}(420.847) = -3.179$, $p = .002$, $SE_{\text{Difference}} = 0.144$, 95% CI [-0.175, -0.302], $d = -0.3$. This result suggests a significant difference between non-entrepreneurs and entrepreneurs in their use of positive and negative words in tweets, as calculated by the difference between positive and negative words (as a percentage) in tweets. There was a statistically significant difference in the delta of positive and negative word use in tweets between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs. This means we can reject the null hypothesis. Entrepreneurs tend to use more positive than negative words as indicators of their positive emotions. Furthermore, Bayesian statistics reveal very strong evidence for this difference: $BF_{10} = 31.66$, $r_{\text{JZS/Cauchy}} = 0.71$, $M = -0.352$, given a 95% highest density interval [-0.544, -0.170]. The BF shown in Fig. 3 reveals that the data were 31.66 times more probable under the alternative hypothesis than the null hypothesis. This can be considered very strong evidence (Jeffreys, 2006) in favor of the alternative hypothesis. Fig. 3 uses boxplots to summarize the overall difference in word usage between non-entrepreneurs and entrepreneurs and Fig. 4 illustrates the Bayesian analysis.

6. Discussion

Although emotions play a prominent role in entrepreneurial endeavors, our knowledge of the effect of emotions on entrepreneurial discovery—strengthening, weakening, or insignificant—remains limited. Fundamentally, according to the findings of two complementary studies entrepreneurial emotions can stimulate and shape the alertness level of entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs which in turn can impact entrepreneurial discovery. In a first U.S.-based study, we analyzed self-reports from 37 entrepreneurs and 54 non-entrepreneurs

Table 8
Study 2: Results of the test statistics between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs.

	Test	Statistic	df	p	VS-MPR*	Location Parameter	SE Difference	95% CI for Location Parameter		Effect Size
								Lower	Upper	
Difference in word usage: positive minus negative, in % of tweeted words	Welch Mann-Whitney	-3.179 19303	420.847	0.002 1.56E-04	35.98 268.457	-0.459 -0.443	0.144	-0.743 -0.676	-0.175 -0.215	-0.3 -0.21
Mean of positive used words per tweet (in %)	Welch Mann-Whitney	-1.938 20592	418.907	0.053 0.005	2.354 14.653	-0.261 -0.304	0.135	-0.526 -0.514	0.004 -0.096	-0.18 -0.16
Mean of negative used words per tweet (in %)	Welch Mann-Whitney	3.063 28305	445.052	0.002 0.004	26.114 16.417	0.198 0.145	0.065	0.071 0.038	0.326 0.251	0.286 0.159
Mean of amount of tweets	Welch Mann-Whitney	-3.333 19987.5	367.354	9.46E-04 0.001	55.839 50.817	-7.282 -7	2.185	-11.579 -11	-2.986 -2.5	-0.32 -0.18
Mean words per tweet	Welch Mann-Whitney	1.194 25234	443.318	0.233 0.548	1.083 1	0.725 0.396	0.608	-0.469 -0.838	1.92 1.692	0.112 0.033
Mean likes per tweet	Welch Mann-Whitney	3.992 43314	263.001	8.51E-05 2.71E-44	461.062 1.36E+41	3228.266 43.977	808.742	1635.83 32.704	4820.7 71.942	0.347 0.774
Mean retweets	Welch Mann-Whitney	3.256 41005.5	263.001	0.001 1.56E-34	43.19 3.03E+31	355.678 4.472	109.24	140.581 2.752	570.78 7.043	0.283 0.679
Amount of tweets	Welch Mann-Whitney	-3.333 19987.5	367.354	9.46E-04 0.001	55.839 50.817	-14.565 -14	4.37	-23.158 -22	-5.972 -5	-0.32 -0.18

Notes. For the Welch t -test, effect size is given by Cohen’s d . For the Mann-Whitney test, effect size is given by the rank biserial correlation. For the Welch t -test, location parameter is given by mean difference. For the Mann-Whitney test, location parameter is given by the Hodges-Lehmann estimate. * Vovk-Sellke Maximum p -Ratio: Based on a two-sided p -value, the maximum possible odds in favor of H_1 over H_0 equals $1/(-e p \log(p))$ for $p \leq .37$ (see JASP).

Fig. 3. Study 2: Boxplots of the results
 Notes. Mean of word usage per tweet per user throughout the time period of tweeting.

Fig. 4. Study 2: Results of Bayesian analysis
 Notes. JASP v. 0.16.2.0 with default effect size priors (Cauchy scale 0.707) has been used. Broad default non-informative priors for all coefficients have been used to reflect the absence of previous knowledge of these parameters' distributions and to have minimal influence on the form of the posterior distributions (Gelman et al., 2008; Kruschke, 2013, 2014). Results are reported using the two-tailed BF with BF_{10} as we expect a difference. Effect size estimates are reported as median posterior Cohen's d with 95% credibility intervals.

who tended to be differently alert to recognizing potential entrepreneurial business opportunities based on positive and negative affect. In particular, our results stress that positive mood, as indicated by such terms as “interested,” “excited,” “enthusiastic,” “inspired,” and “attentive,” facilitates entrepreneurial alertness levels, which increase entrepreneurial discovery. Positiveness thus promotes entrepreneurial discovery of potential business ideas. Overall, based on the PANAS, entrepreneurs tend to exhibit a more positive mood than non-

entrepreneurs, which facilitates entrepreneurs’ levels of alertness and entrepreneurial discovery. The alertness levels of entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs differ considerably which has been confirmed by a complementary field study. In a second study, we explored 28,478 tweets from 2009 through 2021 posted by 185 successful entrepreneurs and 264 non-entrepreneurs, categorizing their tweeted words into positive and negative based on the Harvard IV-4 dictionary. While our results in Study 1 stresses that positiveness supports entrepreneurial

alertness, which accelerates the level of entrepreneurial discovery, Study 2 highlights the significant difference between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs' word usage: successful entrepreneurs tend to use more positive words in their tweets than successful non-entrepreneurs, an observations that confirms that those with higher levels of entrepreneurial alertness and discovery show higher levels of positiveness.

In Study 1, we found very strong evidence (Bayes factor [BF] > 30) for our alternative hypothesis that entrepreneurial alertness facilitates entrepreneurial discovery and that entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs exhibit different levels of alertness and different abilities to discover opportunities. More precisely, Study 1 confirms that only positive affect drives entrepreneurial alertness. Our second field study shows that entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs communicate significantly differently in their use of positive and negative words. To a substantial degree, entrepreneurs tend to use more positive and less negative words. In Study 2 we analyzed only successful entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs to provide a way to distinguish entrepreneurs from non-entrepreneurs in our study; while there is symmetry in opportunities between the groups, there is a difference in whether those opportunities were entrepreneurial. This enabled us to assume that successful non-entrepreneurs also have an ability to envision and exploit opportunities, but not traditionally entrepreneurial ones. By focusing on successful individuals who had earned a public ranking for their success in recognizing opportunities, we build a baseline for success in which the only differences between groups are entrepreneurial versus non-entrepreneurial activities. As to the results of our first study, we are thus able to conclude that entrepreneurial alertness can be boosted by positive emotions and leads to a greater likelihood of discovering potential business opportunities. Because we compare successful entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs who have demonstrated the ability to successfully exploit opportunities, with the only difference being the presence or absence of a purely entrepreneurial context, we can conclude that positive emotions drive alertness, which itself drives entrepreneurial discovery.

To conclude, our work does not replicate the findings of previous studies that use a cross-sectional design (Herron and Sapienza, 1992; Zhou, 2008) which report that negative emotions facilitate alertness. However, those studies did not tackle emotion's effect on the successful exploitation of opportunities in real-world situations. As a consequence, our findings in the lab and in the field significantly enhance this prior work by also taking advantages of Bayesian inference, which allows us to get the very most out of our results, even when they are not statistically significant: we can conclude that expressing more positive than negative emotions over a longer time period, which serves as a proxy for a positive trait, can have beneficial behavioral effects on *entrepreneurial alertness and discovery*.

6.1. Theoretical implications

Understanding how emotions drive the entrepreneurial discovery process provides valuable insights for researchers, entrepreneurship educators, and policymakers in the development of adequate instruments for educating nascent entrepreneurs; it is also valuable for entrepreneurial individuals who wish to facilitate their entrepreneurial discovery. Our work is in line with recent published work related to the expression of positivity by entrepreneurs (Waters et al., 2021) and work that investigated (e.g., Levasseur et al., 2022) how positive emotions are expected to be antecedents of entrepreneurial alertness, which can improve entrepreneurial performance. Our study offers the following three theoretical implications for moving the research field of entrepreneurship forward and might lead us to revisit, extend, and challenge what we have known about entrepreneurial motion and alertness.

First, investigations linked to the antecedents and benefits arising from the relationships of entrepreneurial emotions during entrepreneurial discovery with respect to entrepreneurial alertness are limited in terms of verifying empirical theory (Tang et al., 2012; Cardon et al.,

2013). In this regard, this study enhanced existing theories. For example, Tang et al. (2012) built on McMullen and Shepherd's (2006) work by developing a validated scale for entrepreneurial alertness. In further developing the boundaries of alertness, we have identified positive emotions as important antecedents of alertness, with improved entrepreneurial discovery a central consequence. Carefully articulating the entrepreneurial discovery process by examining positive and negative emotions and drawing on theoretical fundamentals enriches our understanding of antecedents, their impact on entrepreneurial discovery, and the differences in entrepreneurial alertness between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs. Consequently, with the framework developed here, we can more carefully observe the theoretical background of the emotional drivers of entrepreneurial discovery processes. Our theory of entrepreneurial alertness work might not be described as revolutionary (Barney, 2018) because it does not develop an entirely new theory that explicitly rejects the assumptions and logic of prior work and replaces them with different assumptions and a new logic. However, our work has identified a fundamental new question that is essential to answer: If entrepreneurs differ from non-entrepreneurs in cognitive ability, we might assume that they are differently alert to potential entrepreneurial opportunities. This recognition is activated by entrepreneurs' positive emotions, which trigger their ability to make sense of information with an eye to promising entrepreneurial opportunities. Knowledge in this field has thus far remained incomplete, and our study is an important step in filling this gap (Grant and Pollock, 2011).

The second implication is that we have provided empirical evidence for previous theories. Cardon et al. (2013) stress that the development of theories related to emotions into precise strategies for empirical research has faced challenges, which has resulted in a lack of solid evidence. For instance, previous research efforts that examined the complexity of entrepreneurial alertness were limited by scanty empirical investigations (Kang et al., 2010). Although several scholars have formulated theories related to entrepreneurial alertness (Ardichvili et al., 2003; Valliere, 2013), we provide empirical evidence for these theories. Our theoretical evidence stresses the importance of entrepreneurs' cognition, which can be fueled by emotions. Entrepreneurs possess the cognitive ability to envision the future (Kirzner, 1985) triggered by their positive emotions to be confidently enough to take risks. This phenomenon shows similarities to signal detection theory (Swets, 1992), which suggests that the better an entrepreneur's cognitive ability to sense information, the higher the possibility of discovering a successful entrepreneurial opportunity (Tang et al., 2012). We conclude that positive affect strengthens entrepreneurial alertness for opportunity recognition and that there is one possible theoretical explanation for the non-significant effect in H1b related to the missing influence of negative emotions on alertness. Emotions can trigger alertness either consciously or unconsciously, and alertness prepares people to do something. While some studies argue that negative emotions like fear can facilitate discovery, others hold that positive emotions trigger entrepreneurial activities. For instance, prior research shows that dissatisfaction leads to discovery (Herron and Sapienza, 1992; Zhou, 2008). However, we see that negative emotions can also distract, hinder entrepreneurial action, and have less impact on successful opportunity exploitation. Thus, we follow the view of Levasseur et al. (2022) that positive affect has a positive impact on entrepreneurial alertness, with evaluation and judgment positively influencing incremental innovation. Our study contributes to this research stream by providing a balanced viewpoint on both positive and negative affect.

From a third theoretical point of view, self-identification as an entrepreneur has implications because of the two separate representative groups into which individuals placed themselves. The very act of identifying oneself as an entrepreneur increases the frequency or acuity of opportunity recognition. Given the significant differences observed between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs in almost all constructs of interest, but not in self-reported positive and negative affect, indicate a

potential emotional self-identified bias with regard to our results in Study 2. These results clearly highlight entrepreneurs' higher positive emotional state than the one of non-entrepreneurs, while Study 1's positive affect appears to generate more entrepreneurial alertness, which in turn facilitates entrepreneurial discovery. In this regard our work also strengthens the theory of entrepreneurial alertness for opportunity recognition (Tang et al., 2012). By building on Kirzner's (1973, 1999) cognition theory framework, in which alertness is defined as the skill of identifying entrepreneurial opportunities overlooked by others, our distinction between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs and our results emphasize the importance of positive affect, which can act as a naturally but nonconscious occurring stimulus that boosts individuals' perceptual fields and cognitive capacity (Foley and Bates, 2019). Successful entrepreneurs tend to act upon those own emotional stimuli nonconsciously. The path from positive emotions through alertness to entrepreneurial discovery has not been laid out. Our endeavor in this direction offers promising ground for future research.

6.2. Practical implications

We suggest that adopting a higher positive trait affectivity can turn non-entrepreneurs into entrepreneurs. This is important for entrepreneurship educators and how this crucial entrepreneurial trait can impact entrepreneurial career paths. This practical implications of our study relate above all to the crucial role of entrepreneurship in promoting inclusive economic growth (Leydesdorff et al., 2006). We focused on entrepreneurial alertness in the phase of pursuing opportunities and have made important strides in understanding emotions during nascent entrepreneurial activities and how those emotions impact perceived entrepreneurial discovery. Previous researchers focused on the viewpoints of either entrepreneurs or non-entrepreneurs (Chen et al., 2009). By studying both, we have increased our understanding of how entrepreneurial emotions impact discovery via entrepreneurial individuals' alertness. This draws our attention to certain key drivers during idea generation. For instance, nascent entrepreneurs could be trained to favor and cultivate positive emotions to elevate their alertness levels while increasing their chances of accurately sensing entrepreneurial opportunities.

Tang et al. (2012) argue that if individuals draw attention to a positive-driven awareness at will, they can improve their perceptions and interpretations of the surrounding entrepreneurial environment. By facilitating positive emotions, alertness represents a teachable skill that can be enhanced and could thus support nascent entrepreneurs in consciously discovering business ideas with meaningful potential. To conclude, this project will not only alert (entrepreneurial) individuals who wish to improve their entrepreneurial discovery abilities but will also help entrepreneurship educators and policymakers design instruments and services to enhance initiative among nascent entrepreneurs. Frankly, our work highlights the importance of positive emotions for entrepreneurship.

6.3. Limitations

As with any research, this work has limitations. First, Study 1 relies on self-reports. Although previous research into entrepreneurial emotions also use this methodology (Welpe et al., 2012), the situations in Study 1 have not been objectively assessed. However, Study 2 did objectively explore publicly available emotion-sharing activities of entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs. Still, further research is needed to advance the research field by providing, for instance, biophysiological data for measuring emotions during entrepreneurial discovery, which has no subjective influence. In this study, we did select relevant variables and items from different (subjective and objective) sources, but we did not measure those based on the same subject. However, the use of perceptual measures in entrepreneurship is widespread, and previous studies have stressed that subjective and objective measurements are

significantly linked (Murphy and Callaway, 2004). Still, experiments with biophysiological data for measuring emotions objectively would enrich the present analysis. Cardon et al. (2013) stress that it is important for future research to determine whether some individuals (e.g., women or men) naturally exhibit high levels of entrepreneurial emotions before they participate in entrepreneurial actions and whether that could affect entrepreneurial discovery, and even more importantly to what extend in terms of success. To address the contemporary empirical and methodological lacunae in the literature, future studies should collect self-reported behavioral intentions and emotions and gather biophysiological data during real-life situations. Such projects would substantially add to robust theory verification of concepts with unexplored links and empirical findings that have not yet been investigated.

Second, this study has geographic limitations. The relationship between level of emotions and entrepreneurial discovery was examined among individuals in the United States, which may limit generalizability. It is essential to conduct similar investigations in other countries and identify how different individuals' levels of entrepreneurial emotions interact to recommend effective and efficient incentives that could boost regional entrepreneurial activities. Although Study 2 investigates the Twitter accounts of internationally successful entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs, the Twitter API does not store geographical information. Thus, we are not aware of any geographic distribution in this regard, which provides an opportunity for further research.

Third, our sampling strategy could affect external validity of our results, as we focused on lists of people either under 30 years old and of entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs around that age. We made this choice because that group is most likely to have Twitter accounts. Older entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs could display different traits and emotions on Twitter or in general. Future research could replicate our approach with an older cohort or multiple age cohorts. Finally, a fourth limitation is that nobody without a Twitter account was considered in the Study 2 sample.

6.4. Future research

As Shepherd (2015, p. 489) highlights, one of the most promising paths for future entrepreneurship research lies where "the head engages the heart." Our knowledge of entrepreneurial emotions remains limited (Kickul et al., 2009; Tang et al., 2012); thus, entrepreneurial emotions in the pursuit of entrepreneurial opportunity recognition require substantial further elucidation. In particular, the developing research stream on entrepreneurial emotions—specifically, their relation to entrepreneurial discovery—requires further understanding to promote entrepreneurship as an attractive career for individuals and thus adequately support long-term sustainability in the small- and medium-sized enterprises in which entrepreneurs' ingenuity and energy and access to finance are the driving forces. At the same time, our understanding of how entrepreneurial emotions operate in the pursuit of entrepreneurial opportunities—which form the heart of entrepreneurship for such enterprises—requires more attention (Baron, 2006; Shane, 2000; Short et al., 2010). The phase during which new entrepreneurial ideas must be financed is particularly challenging for entrepreneurs (and financiers). Kickul et al. (2009) stress that fuller knowledge of entrepreneurial emotions will help us detect and ideally prevent entrepreneurial shortfalls at an early stage. Thus, entrepreneurial emotions can substantially add to our understanding of how to be alert to entrepreneurial opportunities in a manner that is most beneficial for individuals, firms, and society at large. We hope that this study provides motivation for proceeding on this research path.

Declaration of competing interest

The Author is the founder of the Research and Innovation Management GmbH (RIM), an enterprise focusing on research and innovation projects.

Data availability

Data is available at <https://osf.io/f9sjm/>

Acknowledgments section

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